

ECONOMIC ASPECT OF EFFICIENT USE OF INDUSTRIAL WASTE

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Abstract. *In the article, the political direction of the state, economic approach and environmental situation, environmental issues and environmental biotechnology, the situations of creation of closed systems by the living processes of microorganisms are described.*

Keywords: *Environmental biotechnology, volume of solid, liquid and gaseous wastes, power economy, waste disposal and recycling.*

For the civilized development of every country in the world economy, three main issues are important. They are the political direction of the state, economic approach and environmental situation. The political direction is within the authority of state leaders and politicians, and the economic approach depends on the actions of specialists in this field. And the ecological situation is characterized by the knowledge of scientists. For example, in some cases, unfavorable policies, low level of economic indicators, can lead to a sharp deterioration of environmental conditions. It is clear that this in itself is likely to increase the amount of solid, liquid and gaseous wastes, which are toxic, and which will lead to increased morbidity and mortality. That is why the politics, economy and environmental situation in the country are directly related to each other. These cannot be separated from each other. Changing economics and politics is a natural phenomenon, but stopping or reversing an environmental disaster requires very complex work.

Today, the problem of ecology remains in a complex state. Even now, under the influence of environmental consequences, the generations of people on earth - the third and fourth generation - are becoming biologically weak. And due to the further deterioration of the ecological situation, it is quite possible that people will have genetically unfit, future generations. If such an environmental situation develops further in this direction, it will reach such a point that even late positive policies and powerful economy will not be able to help in the future.

Environmental biotechnology is a scientific and technical direction that includes the use of biotechnology to solve environmental problems:

- wastewater treatment
- solids recycling
- environmental pollution and fighting, etc.

Since the beginning of civilized society, it has faced the problem of environmental protection. Due to human industrial, agricultural and domestic activities, there have been constant changes in the physical, chemical and biological properties of the environment, most of these changes have been very unfavorable. We anticipate that biotechnology will have a diverse and ever-increasing impact on the ways in which we control the environment and its conditions. A good example of this type is the introduction of new, improved methods of waste treatment, but the use of biotechnology in this field is not limited to this. It plays a major role in the chemical industry and agriculture and helps to partially solve many of the problems that exist there.

Today, the life processes of microorganisms create closed systems, wastewater pollution control, in industry, various industries used for the use of alternative energy resources and chemical raw materials are rapidly developing; these processes are widely used in agriculture. Such services, known as "targeted technology" in developing countries, can significantly increase living standards and, most importantly, improve the quality of life for millions of people. The scale of these new biotechnological processes and their application to solving environmental problems can be overwhelming. Biological treatment of waste relies on a number of disciplines - biochemistry, genetics, chemistry, microbiology, chemical technology and computing. The efforts of all these disciplines are concentrated in three main directions:

- 1) degradation of organic and inorganic toxic waste;
- 2) renewal of resources to recycle carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus and sulfur substances;
- 3) obtaining valuable types of organic fuel.

One of the most important issues today is food production. Because as the number of people on the Earth increases, there is a risk of famine. Biotechnology is directly involved in solving this problem. Microbial synthesis of nutrients has also made a significant contribution to food enrichment. Advances in biotechnology are used in plant and animal breeding and protection of agricultural crops from various pests and weeds.

Biotechnology is also involved in solving energy problems. At present, the reduction of oil and gas reserves is observed. In this regard, in order to solve the energy problem in some countries, ways have been found to convert organic matter synthesized by green plants into alcohol and use it as fuel. For example, 75% of all fuel used in Brazil will be produced due to ethanol.

Recently, the production of plastic, which is widely used in everyday life, is being undertaken by processing plant products in a biotechnological way. For example, in Japan, plastic is made on the basis of plant starch. Microorganisms grown in a nutrient medium containing starch produced triglucopolysaccharides. When they are subjected to certain processing, plastic resistant from -30° to $+100^{\circ}$ is obtained. One of the advantages of such plastics is that they do not emit harmful gases when burned, that is, they do not pollute the air. In order to obtain this substance, various wastes of plants are used - sunflower stalks, grain straw, corn cobs, etc. useful.

Environmental protection is one of the most important biotechnological issues. For example, cleaning contaminated water and soil with the help of microorganisms. Likewise, industrial wastes that harm the body can be neutralized with the help of single-celled chlorella algae. Biotechnology is a rapid development due to the achievements of various branches of biological science, especially technical microbiology, genetics and molecular biology.

Modern biology and biotechnology occupy a special place among other areas of scientific and technical progress. That is why the newly started "XXI century is called the century of biology". Achievements in this area are important not only economically, but also socially. Because it is designed to meet human needs.

Waste disposal and recycling

Industrial wastes include any material that is useless in the production process, such as factories, industries, factories, and mining. Types of industrial waste include dirt and gravel, masonry and concrete, scrap metal, oil, solvents, chemicals, wood scraps, and even plant matter from restaurants. Industrial waste can be solid, liquid or gaseous. These can be hazardous or non-

hazardous waste. Hazardous waste can be toxic, flammable, corrosive, reactive, or radioactive. Industrial waste can pollute the air, soil or nearby water sources and eventually end up in the sea. Industrial waste is often mixed with municipal waste, which makes accurate assessment difficult. US estimates reach 7.6 billion tons of industrial waste produced annually. Many countries have enacted legislation to deal with industrial waste, but the strictness and compliance regimes vary. Enforcement is always an issue. How does your trash pick up trash?

Look inside your trash can. How much garbage does your family produce every day? Every week? Where does this garbage go? You might think that the trash we throw away actually goes away, but we know better. Here's a look at what happens to all that trash after you throw it away. Solid waste quick facts and definitions. First, the facts. Did you know that every hour, Americans throw away 2.5 million plastic bottles? Every day, each person living in the United States produces an average of 2 kilograms (about 4.4 pounds) of trash.

Municipal solid waste is defined as waste generated by homes, businesses, schools and other community organizations. This is different from other waste such as construction waste, agricultural waste or industrial waste. We can use three methods to dispose of all this waste - incineration, landfills and recycling.

Digestion is a waste treatment process that involves burning solid waste. In particular, incinerators burn organic materials in the waste stream. A landfill is a hole in the ground for solid waste disposal. Landfills are the oldest and most common method of waste treatment. Recycling is the process of recovering raw materials and reusing them to create new products.

Incineration - solid incineration has several advantages from an environmental point of view. Waste does not take up much space. They do not pollute groundwater. Some plants even use waste heat to generate electricity. Bathing also has a number of disadvantages. They emit several pollutants into the air, and about 10 percent of what is burned is left behind and must be treated in some way. Landfills can be expensive to build and operate.

Sanitary landfills. Before the invention of the landfill, most people living in European communities disposed of their waste on the street or outside the city gates. But sometime in the 1800s, people realized that the animals that attract all this garbage are spreading diseases.

Locals began to collect garbage, which were simply holes in the ground where residents threw garbage. But while it's nice to get rid of the trash on the street, city officials have come to realize that this bad trash still isn't doing any harm. They also leach chemicals from waste materials, creating pollutants called effluents that flow into streams and lakes or are released into local groundwater. In 1976, the US banned the use of these open dumps and established guidelines for the establishment and operation of sanitary landfills. These landfills hold municipal solid waste, as well as construction waste and agricultural waste, preventing pollution of nearby land and water. The main features of the sanitary landfill:

Suppliers: Layers of clay and plastic on the bottom and sides of the landfill to prevent soil runoff. Treatment Treatment: A holding where catchments are collected and treated with chemicals that do not pollute the water. Monitoring Wells: Wells near the landfill that are regularly monitored to ensure that contaminants are not leaching into the water. Compacted Layers: The waste is compacted into layers so that it does not remain uneven. Layers are covered with plastic or clean soil. Vent Pipes: These pipes allow the release of waste gases - methane and carbon dioxide - into the atmosphere to prevent fires and explosions. Once the landfill is filled, it is covered with a clay cap to prevent rainwater from entering. Some are repurposed as parks or

recreation areas, but government regulations prohibit reusing this land for residential or agricultural purposes.

Recycling is another way of handling solid waste, which is to recover raw materials in the waste stream and use them to make new products. Recycling reduces the amount of waste that must be burned or buried. It also reduces pressure on the environment by reducing the need for new resources such as paper and metal. The general trend of creating a new process from recycled, recycled material uses less energy than creating a product using new materials. Fortunately, many materials can be recycled in landfills, such as oil, tires, plastics, paper, glass, batteries, and electronics. Most recycled products fall into four main categories: metal, plastic, paper and glass.

Metal: Most of the metals in aluminum and steel cans are 100 percent recyclable, meaning they can be used again and again to make new cans. However, every year Americans spend 1 billion dollars from aluminum cans. **Plastics:** Plastics are made from solids, or resins left behind from oil (fossil fuels) that have been refined to make gasoline. These resins are then heated, stretched or molded to create everything from bags to bottles to containers. This plastic is easily collected from the waste stream and turned into new products. **Paper:** Most paper products can only be recycled a few times because recycled paper is not as strong or durable as solids. But for every metric ton of paper recycled, 17 trees are saved from logging operations. **Glass:** Glass is one of the easiest materials to recycle and reuse because it can be melted over and over again. Recycled glass can also be cheaper than making it from new materials because recycled glass can be melted at lower temperatures. If you're not already recycling materials before they hit the trash, now is a good time to start. As you can see, every item you take out in your trash has an impact on the planet.

Ecological reliability is the ability of a fairly complete recovery and self-regulation during the successional or evolutionary period of the ecosystem's existence (within diurnal, seasonal, interannual and century natural changes). A simple mechanism for the preservation of ecological stability is the exchange of a species or community that is displaced for a certain reason with another species or community that is ecologically close to them. If there is no such species, it will be replaced by distant species.

Environmental protection is a system of state and public activities aimed at ensuring the harmonious interaction of nature and society based on the improvement of the natural state of the environment, effective use of natural resources, preservation and beautification of natural resources. Sometimes Environmental protection is used interchangeably with the concept of nature protection. But the scope of the concept of nature protection is wider than that of environmental protection; Save the nature.

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